

Moral Appraisals of Generative AI: How Mindset Framing Shapes Moral Judgments, Emotional Appraisals and Privacy Behavior

Abstract

The rapid development of Generative AI (GenAI) and similar technologies has heightened ethical concerns, including privacy issues, discrimination, and data security. However, there is limited understanding of how mindset framing shapes users' moral judgments and emotional responses toward these technologies. To address this gap, this research examines how framing GenAI, particularly in terms of growth or fixed mindset, influences moral appraisals, emotional reactions, and privacy behaviors. Using a mixed-methods approach, this research combines text mining of a large field dataset ($n = 18,035$ reviews) with two experimental studies ($n = 255$ participants). Findings reveal that mindset framing directly influences perceived morality, suggesting that GenAI framed in a growth mindset evokes more positive moral judgments compared to a fixed mindset framing. A growth mindset suggests learning and adaptability, whereas a fixed mindset framing implies that it is immutable and incapable of improvement. Perceived moral judgments mediate the effect of mindset framing (growth vs. fixed) on emotional appraisals. Moreover, mindset framing influences privacy behavior, with participants having low (vs. high) expertise disclosing more under a growth (vs. fixed) mindset. Theoretically, this paper contributes to the literature by integrating key theories on moral judgment, implicit theories, cognitive appraisal theory, and privacy calculus theory, thereby deepening the understanding of moral appraisals regarding GenAI. In practical terms, this research enables organizations to strategically frame GenAI capabilities, positively influencing users' privacy behavior and emotional responses.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, emotional appraisals, implicit mindsets, generative AI, moral judgments, privacy behavior

1. Introduction

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) has garnered increasing attention due to its ability to perform specific tasks more efficiently than humans, resulting in more streamlined processes within organizations across various sectors (Bankins, 2021; Haftor et al., 2024). GenAI tools, such as OpenAI's ChatGPT and Google's Gemini, are widely used to create high-quality content, enabling individuals to generate new ideas and business models, write code, create websites, and improve customer experiences (Cao et al., 2024; McKinsey, 2023). However, the integration of novel AI applications also poses many challenges and risks (Dwivedi et al., 2021; Belk et al., 2023; Puntoni et al., 2021). Nevertheless, recent research suggests that by late 2025, 90% of all online content could be created by GenAI (Marr, 2024).

Despite these advantages of GenAI, its rapid development has raised ethical concerns around bias, discrimination, security, and privacy (Ashok et al., 2022; Huang et al., 2023; Ryan, 2020). Tools like Midjourney can generate deepfakes that spread misinformation and erode public trust (Reuters, 2023). In healthcare, Nabl's chatbot once encouraged self-harm, highlighting the risks of deploying GenAI in sensitive contexts (Simon & Aliferis, 2024). Notably, Microsoft's chatbot Tay mimicked user language, producing offensive content and being shut down within 24 hours (Lee, 2016). Such incidents can provoke moral concerns and negative user reactions (Figueroa-Armijos et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2023). Understanding how individuals judge AI morally—and how emotional appraisals shape these judgments—has become increasingly relevant, given differing perceptions of AI technologies (Chiu et al., 2021; Esmailzadeh & Vaezi, 2022).

Building on these concerns, it is essential to understand not only how people morally evaluate AI but also the psychological mechanisms that shape these evaluations. One promising lens is the theory of implicit mindsets (Blackwell et al., 2007; Dweck et al., 1995), which suggests that individuals differ in their beliefs about whether mental capacities are fixed or malleable. Those with a fixed mindset tend to view abilities as static, while individuals with a growth mindset see them as adaptable and evolving (Murphy & Dweck, 2016). Applied to AI, these beliefs may influence whether users perceive AI systems as ethically improving or inherently flawed (Dang & Liu, 2022a).

As AI is increasingly attributed with intelligent and agentic qualities (Korteling et al., 2021), these mindset-driven perceptions may shape emotional responses and moral judgments—yet they remain largely unexplored. Likewise, in the domain of privacy, where trust and perceived

control are central (Mou & Meng, 2024), mindset framing may alter how users evaluate risks, potentially amplifying concerns or fostering greater disclosure depending on their belief system (Carr et al., 2012).

To date, the underlying psychological mechanism and boundary conditions of how GenAI mindsets may influence emotional appraisals and privacy behavior remain unknown. Relevant to the GenAI context, perceived morality refers to how individuals assess the moral legitimacy of these AI technologies, including whether those systems are aligned with their moral foundations (Graham et al., 2013) and behave in ways that are fair, private, transparent, and responsible (Martin, 2019). Previous studies have linked moral perceptions about AI to emotions, highlighting the importance of emotional appraisals (e.g., Ferrario et al., 2020; Figueroa-Armijos et al., 2023). As such, perceived morality may act as a key mediator in the aforementioned relationships. Additionally, prior experience and knowledge with technology have been found to predict privacy concerns (Ozdemir et al., 2017). Therefore, a user's expertise with GenAI is expected to function as a moderator between mindset framing (growth vs. fixed) and its effect on privacy behavior. To fill these research gaps, this article investigates the following research questions:

RQ1: How does framing GenAI with a growth versus a fixed mindset influence individuals' perceived morality and shape emotional appraisals and privacy behaviors towards GenAI?

RQ2: How does GenAI expertise impact the effect of mindset framing on privacy behavior?

To address these research questions, a mixed-methods approach was employed, combining a text mining study with two experimental studies to evaluate the effects between the constructs. By doing so, this article makes three primary contributions to the literature on GenAI, moral judgments, and privacy behavior. First, it integrates the concept of mindset framing (growth vs. fixed) with moral judgments about GenAI and related technologies. While mindset theory has been extensively studied in relation to human intelligence (Dweck et al., 1995; Murphy & Dweck, 2016) and consumer behavior (Dang & Liu, 2022a), there has been limited research examining how mindset framing influences moral perceptions of GenAI technologies. By framing GenAI as either adaptive (growth mindset) or static (fixed mindset), this research reveals that users assess GenAI's moral legitimacy in alignment with values such as fairness, privacy, and transparency (Graham et al., 2013; Martin, 2019). This insight extends the Implicit Theories of Intelligence (Blackwell et al., 2007; Dweck et al., 1995) to GenAI technology, offering new insights on the role of moral appraisals within this evolving domain.

Second, the research identifies perceived morality as a central mechanism linking mindset framing to downstream effects on emotional appraisals. While previous studies have explored the role of emotions in moral judgments (Greene & Haidt, 2002) and privacy decisions (Ashok et al., 2022), our findings contribute to the literature by providing an integrated perspective on how GenAI mindset framing impacts emotions and behaviors. Building on Cognitive Appraisal Theory (Kemper & Lazarus, 1992) and Privacy Calculus Theory (Dinev & Hart, 2006; Wang et al., 2016), this research is among the first to link mindset framing with both emotional appraisals and privacy behavior in GenAI context.

Third, the study introduces the moderating role of GenAI expertise on the relationship between mindset framing and privacy behavior. By examining distinct levels of user expertise with GenAI, this research reveals how expertise level influences privacy-related choices, particularly the willingness to disclose information (Huisman et al., 2021; Vorobeva et al., 2022). This insight indicates that users with greater expertise may respond to mindset framing by becoming more cautious in privacy behaviors. This contribution fills a critical gap by demonstrating how expertise moderates behavioral responses to GenAI, offering important implications for marketing, information management, and user education related to GenAI.

Overall, by addressing these areas, this research advances the understanding of the psychological mechanisms that shape moral judgments, emotional appraisals, and privacy-related behaviors toward GenAI and other AI-powered technologies.

2. Literature Review

2.1 AI-powered technologies: GenAI and Moral Judgments

AI-powered technologies, such as GenAI, have become essential in various sectors, including healthcare, banking, or urban traffic management (Flavián et al., 2022; Hassan et al., 2019; Wirtz et al., 2021). According to McKinsey & Co. (2023), one of the greatest potentialities of AI tools concerns its application in marketing, personalized suggestions to customers, automated purchasing of advertisements, segmentation and predictive behaviors, which reduces significant costs for companies (Columbus, 2019; Davenport et al., 2020; Gursoy et al., 2019). These benefits have led to novel studies exploring users' moral perceptions of these technologies, for instance, in the artistic field (e.g., GenAI and creativity), product development, innovation, and education. Recent research suggests that the perceived strengths of GenAI positively influence individuals' attitudes, with broad implications for innovation management within organizations (Dwivedi et al., 2021; Mariani & Dwivedi, 2024).

Despite GenAI's potential, users still value human-crafted content creation (Brüns & Meißner, 2024), which impacts GenAI acceptance (Celiktutan et al., 2024). Further research has explored users' resistance to AI-based products, highlighting challenges stemming from both psychological tensions and emotional responses (Flavián et al., 2024; Puntoni et al., 2021). Underlying this resistance is the fact that GenAI carries significant risks and ethical concerns, such as discrimination, social biases, privacy issues, plagiarism, sources of misinformation and ethical dilemmas about authenticity (Amankwah-Amoah et al., 2024; Clegg et al., 2024; De Freitas et al., 2024), which negatively affect users' moral judgments (Hagendorff, 2020; Sullivan & Fosso Wamba, 2022).

2.2. GenAI Morality and Mindset Framing

Drawing on research on implicit mindsets, this study posits that GenAI interactions can be framed in either a growth or fixed mindset. The Implicit Theories of Intelligence (Blackwell et al., 2007; Dweck et al., 1995) state that some adopt a fixed mindset, believing that mental capacities, such as morality and intelligence, are immutable and unchangeable. Others adopt a growth mindset, believing that those capacities are incremental and changeable with effort, experience, and learning (Murphy & Dweck, 2016). Since intelligent capabilities are currently also attributed to AI-based technologies (Korteling et al., 2021), this research drew on the theoretical foundations of Implicit Theories of Intelligence, which have been applied exclusively to human intelligence to date.

Building upon mindset framing literature (e.g., Dweck et al., 1995), this work posits that individuals construe moral and ethical qualities to GenAI on their perceived potential for growth and improvement. Thus, when GenAI is framed in a growth mindset, it is seen as capable of learning and adapting, which can mitigate negative perceptions associated with ethical dilemmas, such as discrimination and privacy risks. Conversely, a fixed mindset framing suggests that GenAI is unchangeable and incapable of improvement (Dang & Liu, 2022a), which may exacerbate ethical concerns, such as privacy issues, and lead to negative moral judgments. Individuals framing technology in a growth mindset are more willing to modify their moral perceptions in response to new knowledge and technological innovations, and they are better equipped to negotiate the complexities of ethical decision-making (Bigman & Gray, 2018; Yeager & Dweck, 2012). On the other hand, those who frame technology in a fixed mindset are more inclined to concentrate on the potential risks associated with AI, which might result in more unfavorable opinions regarding its ethical standing (Kray & Haselhuhn, 2007) and potentially decreasing perceived morality.

2.3 Theoretical Foundation

This paper integrates multiple theoretical perspectives to explain the role of mindset framing in shaping moral judgments, emotional appraisals, and privacy behavior in the context of GenAI. The theories supporting this research include Cognitive Appraisal Theory (Kemper & Lazarus, 1992), Privacy Calculus Theory (Dinev & Hart, 2006; Wang et al., 2016), Implicit Theories of Intelligence (Blackwell et al., 2007; Dweck et al., 1995), and the Personalization-Privacy Paradox (Awad & Krishnan, 2006; Karwatzki et al., 2017). Jointly, these theories provide a comprehensive foundation to evaluate how GenAI mindset framing (growth vs. fixed) affects emotional appraisals (H1a) and privacy behavior (H1b), the mediating role of perceived morality (H2), and the moderating role of GenAI expertise (H3).

2.3.1 GenAI Mindset Framing and Emotional Appraisals

According to the Cognitive Appraisal Theory, individuals who frame GenAI in a growth mindset—characterized by optimism about learning and adaptability—are more inclined to view these AI-based technologies as possible instruments for problem-solving (Dweck, 2006; Kemper & Lazarus, 1992), resulting in positive emotional appraisals (Ameen et al., 2021; Blackwell et al., 2007). In contrast, those who frame GenAI in a fixed mindset tend to focus on its limitations, such as biases or lack of transparency, which diminishes perceived morality and leads to negative emotional responses (Burnette et al., 2013; Kray & Haselhuhn, 2007). Consequently, this research suggests that emotional responses to GenAI depend on the mindset framing. In other words, we predict that framing GenAI in a growth mindset enhances positive moral appraisals, such as flexibility, capacity for learning, and improvement. In contrast, fixed mindset framing implies static capabilities, which may reinforce ethical concerns and result in negative moral appraisals (Blackwell et al., 2007; Dweck et al., 1995; Haidt, 2001). Accordingly:

H1a: Framing GenAI in a growth (vs. fixed) mindset leads to positive downstream effects on emotional appraisals.

2.3.2 GenAI Mindset Framing and Privacy Behavior

Privacy issues can be a significant obstacle to the effectiveness of AI-based technologies, as they rely on the disclosure of personal data to provide users with personalized information during interactions (Kronemann et al., 2023). Privacy, in the context of GenAI, refers to the control and awareness that users have regarding the way their personal data is collected, used, or stored (Hann et al., 2007). Research on information disclosure has been shaped by the view

that privacy is a personal responsibility, emphasizing the need for individuals to manage the collection, use, and sharing of their data (Pomfret et al., 2020), which affects attitudes and willingness to share information (Grewal et al., 2021).

Privacy Calculus Theory (Dinev & Hart, 2006; Wang et al., 2016) explains how users weigh the benefits (e.g., enhanced services) against risks (e.g., privacy loss) when deciding to share personal information with AI-based systems. Individuals are less likely to share data if they have privacy concerns or perceive significant risks (Kronemann et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2009). However, they are more willing to disclose information when they perceive minimal privacy risks (Sun et al., 2015).

Since privacy is a significant concern in the context of AI (Mou & Meng, 2024), it is pertinent to note how mindset framing influences not only emotional responses but also privacy behavior. The Implicit Theories of Intelligence (Blackwell et al., 2007; Dweck et al., 1995) provides a foundation for understanding how a growth mindset framing can evoke trust and reduce anxiety, encouraging more open privacy behaviors and greater willingness to share information. Conversely, a fixed mindset framing may amplify concerns and defensive responses, reducing trust and openness (Carr et al., 2012). By integrating these theories, it is possible to examine the effect of GenAI mindset framing on the trade-off between privacy concerns and perceived technological benefits. We argue that when GenAI technology is framed in a growth (as opposed to fixed) mindset, individuals may exhibit a more open attitude towards its privacy, being more willing to disclose data. Conversely, a fixed mindset framing may lead to caution and privacy-protective behaviors. Thus, more formally:

H1b: Framing GenAI in a growth (vs. fixed) mindset leads to positive downstream effects on privacy behavior.

2.3.3 GenAI Morality and Emotional Appraisals

Moral judgments are expected to serve as a key underlying process in shaping individuals' emotional responses to GenAI mindset framing. Research in moral psychology suggests that individuals employ both intuitive and reasoning processes to evaluate the moral implications of their actions (Haidt, 2001). For example, if users determine that an AI system discriminates against a particular group, their moral perception is that the system is unethical (Bigman & Gray, 2018). Furthermore, Moral Foundations Theory posits that moral perceptions are grounded in six key foundations: care and harm, fairness and cheating, loyalty and betrayal,

authority and subversion, purity and degradation, and liberty and oppression (Graham et al., 2013). Overall, these findings suggest that users can hold both positive and negative perceptions regarding morality. Those who frame GenAI in a growth mindset are more likely to view it as morally sound and respond more favorably (Longoni et al., 2019). As such, perceived morality may be a key mediator that shapes emotional appraisals of GenAI. These relationships were explored in our studies to evaluate whether, by framing GenAI in a growth mindset, individuals can attribute higher moral judgements to their capabilities, reinforcing positive emotional responses. Accordingly:

H2: Perceived moral judgments mediate the relationship between framing GenAI in a growth (vs. fixed) mindset and positive downstream effects on emotional appraisals.

2.3.4 The Moderating Role of GenAI Expertise

While AI-based technologies initially appeared harmless, they can now be seen as privacy invaders due to their excessive or unnecessary collection of personal data (Du & Xie, 2021). Privacy is crucial when using GenAI applications that collect substantial amounts of data during user interactions, and to understand the factors that influence users' willingness to disclose information to these systems (Belanche et al., 2024). According to the Personalization-Privacy Paradox (Awad & Krishnan, 2006; Karwatzki et al., 2017), a contradiction arises when individuals assess the benefits and risks of disclosing their information, expressing privacy concerns, yet still share personal data with GenAI applications. This suggests that users consider the privacy concerns against the benefits they can gain from personalizing recommendations (Aguirre et al., 2015; Bornschein et al., 2020).

This study further aims to extend the literature by examining whether users' GenAI expertise (i.e., level of knowledge about GenAI) serves as a moderator between GenAI mindset framing and their privacy behaviors. Prior experiences and awareness have been shown to predict privacy concerns in technological settings (Ozdemir et al., 2017). For users with low GenAI expertise, emotional responses triggered by a growth mindset framing (Dang & Liu, 2022a) are more likely to result in reduced privacy concerns. This is grounded on research showing negative association between lack of knowledge about a technology and privacy concerns (Van Dyke, 2007). Meanwhile, for users with high GenAI expertise, who may better understand the risks associated with personal data sharing (e.g., potential misuse of data), these emotional responses may be diminished, leading to heightened privacy behaviors regardless of the mindset

framing (Longoni et al., 2023). Indeed, prior work demonstrates that experience enhances awareness of potential risks, thereby increasing privacy concerns (Li, 2014).

GenAI expertise is a crucial variable in assessing the moral appraisals of new technologies, as the emotional responses triggered by a specific mindset framing (Dang & Liu, 2022a) are likely to lead to different privacy behaviors. Hence, the more knowledge individuals have about GenAI, the better they can assess both its capabilities and the risks (e.g., misuse of personal data by GenAI algorithms). High-expertise users may thus exhibit skepticism or critical evaluation that diminishes the framing's influence, due to their understanding of GenAI's inherent limitations and potential risks. Overall, expertise is expected to shape the way individuals interpret and react to GenAI. Therefore, under low expertise, we expect that growth (vs. fixed) mindset framing leads to higher willingness to disclose data on privacy behavior. However, under high expertise, we posit that individuals who frame GenAI in a Growth (vs. fixed) mindset are less likely to share information with a GenAI application, as they are aware of the risks that raise privacy concerns. More formally:

H3: GenAI expertise (high vs. low) has a moderating effect in the relationship between the GenAI mindset framing (growth vs. fixed) and the downstream effects on privacy behavior.

3. Research Design

3.1 Overview of studies

This research employs a mixed-methods approach, integrating three studies: a large text mining qualitative dataset ($n = 18,035$ reviews) and two controlled experimental studies ($n = 255$ participants). This research aims to investigate whether users' moral perceptions of AI, particularly General AI (GenAI), are positively influenced by growth mindset framing versus fixed mindset framing.

Study 1 employs text mining to provide initial evidence for our core prediction that individuals perceive GenAI tools as more morally acceptable when these are framed in a growth mindset (vs. a fixed mindset). Additionally, we investigate whether perceived morality serves as a mediator between mindset framing and emotional appraisals (H2).

Study 2 provides further support for our hypotheses, in a controlled experiment investigating whether growth (vs. fixed) mindset framing leads to positive emotional appraisals (H1a), and if these downstream effects are impacted by higher (vs. lower) perceived morality about AI-based technology. It also assesses whether moral appraisals operate under AI and human agents.

Consistent with our theorizing, growth (as opposed to fixed) mindsets yield stronger moral appraisals for artificial agents compared to human agents.

Study 3 examined whether the fact that users frame GenAI in a growth (vs. fixed) mindset leads to differences in privacy behavior (H1b). Furthermore, Study 3 examined the moderator effect of GenAI expertise (high vs. low) on the relationship between GenAI mindset framing (growth vs. fixed) and its impact on privacy behavior (H3). Consistent with current research best practices, the two experimental studies were pre-registered at Aspredicted.org: Study 2 (#155240) and Study 3 (#192627).

3.1.1 Study 1: Field evidence for the role of mindsets (growth and fixed) and perceived morality on emotional appraisals

The purpose of this study was twofold. First, it aimed to test the prediction that users have a higher perceived morality regarding GenAI tools when they are framed in a growth mindset, as opposed to a fixed mindset. In addition, it aimed to examine whether perceived morality serves as an underlying mechanism linking AI mindset framing and emotional appraisals.

Procedures

This study employed a text-mining procedure, relying on field data collected from reviews of ChatGPT users on both the Google Play and Apple App Store. To obtain the reviews, a Python script was developed to systematically scrape and consolidate 169,017 reviews of ChatGPT from the United States. Then, the standard procedure in the field was followed (e.g., Berger, Humphreys, and Schweidel, 2020) to ensure an organized dataset for analysis. The Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) library was utilized to remove duplicate entries and empty rows, thereby eliminating redundancy and missing information. Non-textual information, such as numbers and special characters, was also removed to focus solely on the textual content. Stopwords - such as 'the', 'and', 'as', etc. that do not contribute with significant meaning were filtered out - to enhance the relevance of the data. Language detection was employed to keep only reviews written in English, and a lemmatization technique was applied to reduce words to their root form, as well as tokenization to split the text into individual words or tokens. This preprocessing phase ensured that the dataset was clean, consistent, and ready for accurate analysis.

Measures

Independent variable.

The independent variable was GenAI mindset framing (i.e., fixed or growth) by the users. To determine whether users wrote reviews framing GenAI in a specific mindset, a script was developed to classify reviews into fixed or growth mindset categories, respectively.

First, a list of words related to both mindsets was developed, drawing upon prior conceptual work (e.g., Ortiz Alvarado et al., 2024; Scherer & Campos, 2022). These words were then matched against the reviews and weighted using Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF), a numerical statistic that reflects the importance of a word within a collection of documents (Danyal et al., 2024). The TF-IDF scores were computed using the `TfidfVectorizer` function from the `sklearn` library (Pedregosa, 2011) with specific parameter settings: unigram representation (`ngram_range=(1,1)`) to capture individual word importance, `min_df=1` to ensure all words appearing at least once were considered. The resulting TF-IDF scores were stored in a dictionary and applied to the predefined word lists for fixed and growth mindsets. If a word did not appear in the TF-IDF matrix, it was assigned a default weight of 1.

To enhance classification accuracy, a supervised machine learning model was employed. The text data was first vectorized using `CountVectorizer`, converting the cleaned reviews into a matrix of token counts. The dataset was then split into training and testing sets, using an 80-20 ratio (`train_test_split(test_size=0.2, random_state=42)`). A Logistic Regression model was trained on the labeled data, leveraging learned patterns in textual content to improve classification beyond the dictionary-based method.

Model performance was assessed using precision, recall, and F1-score. The classification model demonstrated strong performance in distinguishing between reviews with a fixed and growth mindset. The logistic regression model achieved an overall accuracy of 99.02%, indicating a high degree of reliability in classification. The precision, recall, and F1-score metrics further support the model's robustness. For reviews classified as Fixed, the model achieved a precision of 0.99, a recall of 0.93, and an F1-score of 0.96. Similarly, for Growth mindset reviews, the precision was also 0.99, with a recall of 1.00 and an F1-score of 0.99. The confusion matrix indicates that only 24 fixed-mindset reviews were misclassified as Growth, and 4 growth-mindset reviews were misclassified as fixed, confirming the model's robustness.

Additionally, reverse coding was implemented to account for antonyms, ensuring that words with opposite meanings were appropriately weighted. Negations were handled by appending negation words (e.g., "not") to the subsequent word to maintain their negated meaning (e.g.,

"not good" to "not_good"). Then, the occurrences of weighted fixed and growth mindset words within each review were counted, including reverse-coded terms.

Finally, reviews were classified as fixed, growth, or neutral, applying a percentage difference threshold. For the sake of balance, only reviews with either a fixed or growth mindset were included in the analysis. Therefore, reviews categorized as neutral were removed, and the final dataset contained 18,035 reviews.

Dependent Variable.

The dependent variable (i.e., emotional appraisals) was computed by running a sentiment analysis on the reviews using the VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner) sentiment analysis tool from the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK). The VADER algorithm is commonly used to quantify and categorize the sentiment of text, such as reviews (Borg & Boldt, 2020) and categorizes texts into positive, negative, or neutral.

Mediator.

This study aimed to test whether perceived morality underlies the relationship between GenAI mindset framing and emotional appraisals. To calculate the mediator, a dictionary-based text analysis (Humphreys & Wang, 2018) was employed to compute a morality score for each review based on the Moral Foundations Dictionary (MFD) (Frimer et al., 2019). This dictionary is based on the moral values articulated in the Moral Foundations Theory (Graham et al. 2011, 2013). The MFD posits that the sense of morality is structured around six moral foundations: Care/Harm, Fairness/Cheating, Loyalty/Betrayal, Authority/Subversion, Purity/Degradation, and Liberty/Oppression. Hence, a list of positive and negative words related to morality was defined, and a morality score was calculated for each review. If a word was negated (e.g., prefixed with "not"), the function reversed its typical impact on the score.

Covariates.

Given the observational nature of the dataset, we included covariates to control for potential confounding variables that might influence the relationship between mindset framing and emotional appraisals. Three covariates were considered: review source, rating, and year of submission. The review source (i.e., Google Play or Apple App Store) was included to control for user behavior and review styles, which may differ between platforms (e.g., Berger, Humphreys, & Schweidel, 2020).

The rating (1 to 5 stars) was also used as a covariate because previous literature indicates that extreme ratings are often associated with more polarized sentiments, which could

systematically influence emotional appraisals and perceived morality (Chevalier & Mayzlin, 2006). Users providing very low or very high ratings may express their evaluations with stronger emotional intensity, potentially confounding the effects attributed to mindset framing.

Finally, the review submission year was included to address temporal variations in users' perceptions of AI-powered tools. Since ChatGPT was launched in late 2022, user attitudes and expectations toward the technology may have evolved as updates were introduced and adoption increased. By controlling for the review year, we ensured that observed effects were not influenced by broader shifts in AI sentiment over time.

Results and Discussion

The analysis started by employing a Coarsened Exact Matching (CEM), which is a statistical technique used to improve the comparability of treatment and control groups in observational studies (Iacus et al., 2012). CEM temporarily coarsens the data into broader categories and matches units exactly within these categories. After matching, the data is returned to its original form, but only the matched units are kept, which ensures that the groups are balanced on the covariates. Overall, CEM is an effective approach for achieving balance and reducing bias in studies where randomization is not feasible (Blackwell et al., 2009).

Before matching the data, the Standardized Mean Difference (SMD) for the 'rating' was 1.0585, indicating a significant imbalance. After matching, the SMD became 0, which shows that the matching process effectively balanced this covariate. Similarly, the SMD for the 'source' decreased from 0.0604 to 0, and 'year' from 0.0740 to 0. The results were significant in the Bayesian ANOVA ($BF = 7.445$), showing that the matched groups were adequately balanced.

Results from Chi-Square in the matched dataset sustained the core prediction that framing GenAI in a mindset (growth or fixed) impacts emotional appraisals. Specifically, 86% of reviews in which a positive sentiment was attributed came from users framing ChatGPT in a growth mindset; on the other hand, 61.4% of reviews in which a negative sentiment was attributed came from users that framed ChatGPT in a fixed mindset ($\chi^2_{(18025)} = 1594.42, p < .001$). In addition, results from a Two Sample T-test indicated that users framing ChatGPT in a growth mindset have a higher perceived morality towards it ($M = .54, SD = .60$) than those who frame ChatGPT in a fixed mindset ($M = .11, SD = .44, t_{(18023)} = -39.56, p < .001$).

To test whether perceived morality mediates the relationship between GenAI mindset framing and emotional appraisals, a mediation analysis was run using the Macro Process of Hayes (Hayes, 2013), using model 4 to estimate a 95% confidence interval for the indirect effect, with

5,000 bootstrapped samples. As expected, the indirect effect was significant ($\beta = .08$, CI: [.0702 to .0823]).

The results of pilot study confirmed what is proposed by H1a. Users that framed GenAI applications (i.e. ChatGPT) in a growth (vs. fixed) mindset perceived those technologies with higher moral judgments. Furthermore, analyzing the mediation effect of perceived morality, it was observed that participants that frame GenAI in a growth mindset reveal positive downstream effects on emotional appraisals (H1a and H2).

3.1.2 Study 2: The mediation effect of perceived morality in the relationship between mindset framing and emotional appraisals.

The purpose of Study 2 was threefold: first, we wanted to gather additional evidence to support our hypothesis, which proposes that framing GenAI in a growth (vs. fixed) mindset leads to better emotional responses (H1a). Second, we wanted to test whether the relationship between AI mindset framing (growth or fixed) and emotional appraisals about AI is mediated by perceived morality (H2). Lastly, we included a human agent condition to confirm that our theorizing about moral appraisals applies specifically to artificial entities, ensuring that the effects observed are unique to AI rather than human agents.

Design and Procedures

We recruited 120 Portuguese participants on Prolific for a 2 (agent: human vs. AI) by 2 (mindset: growth vs. fixed) between-subjects experiment, in exchange for a small fee, to participate in the study. Each participant received \$0.40 (approx. €0.35) for completing a 5-minute questionnaire, corresponding to an average hourly rate of \$8. One participant was excluded for failing the attention check. Hence, our final sample included 119 participants who were randomly assigned to one of four conditions: AI Growth Mindset ($n = 28$, 23.53%), AI Fixed Mindset ($n = 29$, 24.37%), Human Growth Mindset ($n = 32$, 26.89%), and Human Fixed Mindset ($n = 30$, 25.21%). Participants ranged from 20 to 59 years ($M_{\text{age}} = 29.79$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 8.97$). 62.2% of respondents were male, 37% female, and .8% non-binary (see more details in Table 1). The sample was relatively balanced across conditions, ensuring a robust experimental design and comparable group sizes for meaningful statistical analysis.

To provide evidence that perceived morality and emotional appraisals about AI are influenced by the mindset in which AI is framed, we manipulated the mindset framing by reminding participants of AI capabilities (growth vs. fixed) and contrasted them with a condition of human

intelligence capabilities (growth vs. fixed). Participants were exposed to a written scenario about AI technology (vs. human intelligence) (see details in the Appendix) and asked to recall and describe a situation related to it. The manipulations were adapted from the literature about Implicit Theories of Intelligence (Blackwell et al., 2007; Dweck et al., 1995) and modified to fit the context of Artificial Intelligence in the AI scenarios.

Table 1. Sample and demographic characteristics of participants in experimental studies

Study	N	Gender	(%)	Age	Condition	Sample (%)
2	119	Male	62.2	M = 30.16, SD = 1.09	AI Growth Mindset	23.53
		Female	37.0	M = 29.36, SD = 1.31	AI Fixed Mindset	24.37
		Non-Binary	0.8	21	Human Growth Mindset	26.89
		Not disclosed	0.0	-	Human Fixed Mindset	25.21
3	136	Male	62.5	M = 36.89, SD = 1.21		
		Female	33.1	M = 39.47, SD = 1.86	GenAI Growth Mindset	47.06
		Non-Binary	3.7	M = 27.20, SD = 3.35	GenAI Fixed Mindset	52.94
		Not disclosed	0.7	32		

Measures

After the priming question, participants answered two sets of questions. The first questions measured emotional appraisals regarding AI, with twenty items adapted from Watson et al. (1988), using a Likert scale ranging from 1 (not at all) to 9 (extremely) (e.g., *How do you feel about Artificial Intelligence? - "Inspired"*). Some items, which represented a negative appraisal (e.g., upset, guilty, hostile, etc.) were reverse-coded to ensure normalization, and the items were averaged to create an emotional appraisal index ($\alpha = .86$), so that higher scores represented higher appraisals. The second set of questions measured the dimensions of perceived morality of AI and replicated the ones applied in Study 1, using a Likert Scale with nine items adapted from the Moral Foundations Theory (Graham et al., 2011, 2013) ($\alpha = .82$) (see details in the Appendix). We also added a manipulation-check question (i.e., *Would you consider the scenario you read at the beginning of this survey to be about...1 (Human intelligence) to 9 (Artificial intelligence), and 1 (growth mindset) to 9 (fixed mindset)*). At the end, participants answered demographic questions.

Results and Discussion

The findings offer a critical view of the Implicit Theories of Intelligence applied to AI and highlight the role of moral judgments in shaping users' perceptions and responses to these

technologies. The manipulation checks confirmed that participants accurately distinguished between AI and human agents and correctly perceived the mindset conditions as either fixed or growth. Participants assigned to the AI scenarios noticed that the agent was an AI ($M = 8.23$, $SD = 1.65$) as opposed to participants assigned to the human agent ($M = 3.08$, $SD = 2.4$, $t_{(117)} = -13.51$, $p < .001$, $d = 2.08$). In addition, participants in the fixed mindset condition correctly perceived the manipulation as fixed ($M = 8.22$, $SD = 1.64$) compared to those in the growth mindset condition ($M = 2.03$, $SD = 1.83$, $t_{(117)} = 19.4$, $p < .001$, $p = 1.74$). Hence, we ensured that our manipulations were successful.

Results from a two-way ANOVA (see more details in Table 2) with the emotional appraisals index as the dependent variable, and agent type (human vs. AI) and mindset (fixed vs. growth) as factors, show a non-significant direct effect of the agent ($F_{(1,115)} = 2.2$, $p = .14$) and a non-significant effect of the mindset ($F_{(1,115)} = .80$, $p = .37$). However, a key finding of this study is the significant interaction effect between agent type and mindset framing on emotional appraisals ($F_{(1,115)} = 6.27$, $p = .01$, $d = .47$). Specifically, planned contrasts show that when the mindset was framed as growth, the emotional appraisals were higher for the AI agent ($M = 6.33$, $SD = 1.09$) than for the human agent ($M = 5.6$, $SD = .91$, $p = .006$). When the mindset was framed as fixed, there was no difference between agents (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Means of emotional appraisals by agent and by mindset

These results show that whether framing AI or humans in a fixed mindset, there are no significant differences in emotional responses because individuals tend to focus on the limitations in both cases. Conversely, when AI is framed in a growth mindset, it gets a better

emotional response because AI is able to perform several tasks better than humans and provides answers more quickly and efficiently, with more positive results for users (Bankins, 2021; Blackwell et al., 2007; Dang & Liu, 2022a; Dweck et al., 1995; Haftor et al., 2024; Murphy & Dweck, 2016). This reveals a new theorization of the Implicit Theories of Intelligence associated with artificial agents and how it shapes perceived morality and emotional appraisals of AI. In this research, the type of mindset (growth or fixed) is unique when attributed to artificial agents.

In addition, results from a two-way ANOVA (see more details in Table 2) with perceived morality as the dependent variable, agent type (human vs. AI) and mindset (fixed vs. growth) as independent variables, show a significant main effect of the agent ($F_{(1,115)} = 5.74, p = .02$), and a non-significant main effect of mindset ($F_{(1,115)} = .31, p = .58$). Furthermore, the 2x2 interaction was significant ($F_{(1,115)} = 4.02, p = .047$). Specifically, AI was perceived as more moral under a growth mindset ($M = 5.24, SD = .22$) as compared to a fixed mindset ($M = 4.69, SD = .21, p = .05$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Means of perceived morality by agent and by mindset

When humans are framed in a growth mindset, the perceived morality differs from when AI is framed in the same mindset. Unlike previous theories applied to human intelligence (e.g., Dang & Liu, 2022a; Dweck et al., 1995), this research has theorized that higher perceived morality, depending on the growth mindset framing, was only observed when AI agents were framed in this manner.

Next, we examined whether emotional appraisals about AI can be explained by perceived morality by running a moderated mediation analysis using the PROCESS Macro of Hayes (model 8), with 5,000 bootstrap samples and 95% confidence intervals (Hayes, 2013). Our model used the agent as an independent variable, emotional appraisals as the dependent variable, perceived morality as a mediator, and mindset as a moderator. Results indicate that perceived morality works as an underlying condition in the growth mindset ($\beta = .31$, CI: [.0955 to .6044]), but not in the fixed mindset ($\beta = .03$, CI: [-.1858 to .2463]). Overall, the moderated mediation model was significant ($\beta = .28$, CI: [.0048 to .6451]). This suggests that when AI is framed as in a growth mindset, individuals perceive it as more moral, which in turn enhances their emotional appraisals. Notably, this mediation effect was absent in the fixed mindset condition, suggesting that moral perceptions do not influence emotional responses in a fixed mindset.

Table 2. Results of the ANOVA

Study	Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	F	Sig.
2	Emotional appraisals	Agent type (human vs. AI)	2.2	0.14
		Mindset (fixed vs. growth)	0.8	0.37
		Agent Type * Mindset $M_{\text{Growth*AI}} > M_{\text{Growth*human}}$	6.27	0.01**
2	Perceived morality	Agent type (human vs. AI)	5.74	0.02**
		Mindset (fixed vs. growth)	0.31	0.58
		Agent Type * Mindset $M_{\text{Growth*AI}} > M_{\text{fixed*AI}}$	4.02	0.04*
3	Privacy Behavior (willingness to disclose information)	Mindset (fixed vs. growth)	2.2	0.38
		GenAI expertise (high vs. low)	0.31	0.58
		Mindset * GenAI expertise $M_{\text{growth*low expertise}} > M_{\text{fixed*low expertise}}$	4.47	0.04*

Note: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$

Study 2 sheds some light on previous research regarding emotional appraisals (Kemper & Lazarus, 1992; So et al., 2015) by revealing the effect of mindset framing. These results

indicated that participants who framed AI in a growth (vs. fixed) mindset demonstrated higher moral perceptions of AI and showed more positive emotional appraisals.

3.1.3 Study 3: The moderating role of GenAI expertise in the relationship between mindset framing and privacy behavior.

Extending our previous studies, Study 3 tested whether GenAI mindset framing impacts the downstream effects on privacy behavior (H1b), since privacy and data disclosure are a major concern for users that interact with GenAI applications (e.g., ChatGPT). Furthermore, Study 3 examined whether GenAI expertise works as a boundary condition in the relationship between mindset framing and privacy behavior (H3).

Design and Procedures

We recruited 142 US participants from CloudResearch to take part in this 2 (mindset type: growth vs. fixed) by 2 (GenAI expertise: high vs. low) between-subjects experiment. Each participant received \$0.40 (approx. €0.35) for completing a 5-minute questionnaire, corresponding to an average hourly rate of \$8. After deleting those who failed our attention check, as per the pre-registered procedure, our final sample consisted of 136 subjects who were randomly assigned to one of two experimental conditions: GenAI Growth Mindset ($n = 64$, 47.06%) and GenAI Fixed Mindset ($n = 72$, 52.94%). All the respondents were American, and their age ranged from 18 to 65 years ($M_{\text{age}} = 37.35$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 11.65$). 62.5% of participants were male, 33.1% female, 3.7% non-binary, and .70% preferred not to answer gender information (see more details in Table 1).

We initially activated the mindset framing by describing a situation in which they would use a GenAI-powered travel app named “FindHotel”, with high (vs. low) machine learning to deeply (vs. softly) analyze extensive (vs. limited) consumer information to provide personalized travel recommendations. These scenarios were adapted from the literature about Implicit Theories of Intelligence (Blackwell et al., 2007; Dweck et al., 1995) and developed to fit the context of GenAI (see details in the Appendix).

Measures

After the priming question, we measured the privacy behavior (willingness to disclosure personal data) using a Likert scale with items ranging from 1 (not at all) to 9 (extremely), using three items adapted from Zhang et al., (2023) (e.g., “*I am willing to reveal my data with FindHotel app*”, $\alpha = .97$).

Finally, there was a multiple-choice question to assess the GenAI expertise level, using six items adapted from literature (Huisman et al., 2021; Vorobeva et al., 2022) that measures the knowledge about GenAI, ranging from “*Never heard of Generative AI*” to “*Active Generative AI research/development*” (see details in the Appendix).

In addition, we included a manipulation check question, using a multiple-choice question which was “*The scenario you read at the beginning of this survey is related to...?*”. The two options were either “*Growth Algorithm: high-performance travel app (capabilities can be developed and deep personal data use)*” or “*Fixed Algorithm: low performance travel app (capabilities are limited and soft personal data use)*”. At the end, there were some demographic questions.

Results and Discussion

The results provide an understanding of how mindset framing and GenAI expertise influence privacy-related decisions. The manipulation checks confirmed effective mindset framing, with 82.66% of participants in the growth mindset condition selecting the correct alternative, as well as 96.72% of participants in the fixed mindset condition correctly identifying their assigned mindset ($\chi^2_{(135)} = 85.1, p < .001$). Hence, we ensured that our manipulations were successful.

Furthermore, results from a two-way ANOVA with mindset and GenAI expertise as independent variables (see Table 2 for more details) and privacy behavior as the dependent variable revealed no significant main effect of mindset framing or GenAI expertise on privacy behavior, indicating that these factors alone do not directly influence disclosure behavior. Specifically, the data analysis showed a non-significant main effect of the mindset ($F_{(1,131)} = 2.2, p = .38$) and a non-significant main effect of expertise ($F_{(1,131)} = .31, p = .58$). However, it showed a significant 2x2 interaction ($F_{(1,131)} = 4.47, p = .04$) which highlights that the impact of mindset framing depends on GenAI expertise levels. Planned contrasts reveal that participants who had low GenAI expertise showed higher willingness to disclose information in the growth mindset condition ($M = 2.52, SD = 1.79$) in contrast with participants in the fixed mindset condition ($M = 1.58, SD = 1.57, p < .05$). This suggests that when individuals believe that GenAI can improve and adapt over time, they are more likely to share data to facilitate its development. However, this effect diminishes for those with a fixed mindset, where individuals may see little personal or technological benefit in sharing their data.

Conversely, for individuals with high GenAI expertise, a reversed pattern emerged. Those in the fixed mindset condition showed a higher willingness to disclose information ($M = 2.32, SD = 1.72$) compared to those in the growth mindset condition ($M = 2.03, SD = 1.59, p < .05$).

(Figure 3). This finding is particularly interesting because it suggests that individuals with high expertise in GenAI may feel more confident about their ability to control data-related risks within a fixed mindset framework. When they believe GenAI is static and not susceptible to learning, they may perceive disclosure as less risky. However, in the growth mindset condition, their greater awareness of GenAI's advancing capabilities and potential data vulnerabilities could lead them to exercise more caution in sharing information.

Figure 3. Means of privacy behavior by GenAI expertise and by mindset

These findings reveal a key relationship between mindset framing and GenAI expertise. Individuals with less expertise are more open to sharing data when they have a growth mindset. In comparison, those with more expertise tend to be more cautious, likely due to a better understanding of data security and privacy risks. Conversely, a fixed mindset makes novices less willing to share their data. However, surprisingly, it has the opposite effect on experts, who may feel they have greater control over their information. These results challenge the notion that a growth mindset consistently promotes openness, underscoring the influence of domain knowledge on privacy behaviors.

Overall, this study extends our understanding of how mindset framing impacts privacy behavior, showing that individuals with higher GenAI expertise are less likely to share information when framed in a growth mindset due to awareness of privacy risks (Awad & Krishnan, 2006; Karwatzki et al., 2017). Conversely, less knowledgeable users are more willing

to share information in a growth mindset, as they are less aware of the associated risks and more willing to contribute to technology's learning (Dang & Liu, 2022a; Murphy & Dweck, 2016).

4. Discussion

Although recent research highlights ethical constraints in AI-based applications across various sectors (Huang et al., 2023), the literature on perceived morality and its influence on emotional appraisals toward GenAI remains scarce. The findings reveal that framing AI and GenAI in a growth (vs. fixed) mindset leads to more positive emotional appraisals among users, indicating that perceived morality mediates this effect. These findings contribute to research on moral appraisals (Kranzbühler et al., 2020; Sullivan & Fosso Wamba, 2022), highlighting the importance of moral judgments and emotional appraisals regarding AI-powered technologies, particularly GenAI. Additionally, our findings provide support for the moderating effect of GenAI expertise on privacy behavior, revealing that participants with low (vs. high) GenAI expertise were more willing to disclose information in the growth (vs. fixed) mindset condition. Moreover, when framing GenAI in a growth mindset, individuals with greater expertise about GenAI are less likely to share their data with a GenAI application.

4.1 Theoretical contributions and implications

The findings contribute to the literature by integrating and applying theories on morality (Greene & Haidt, 2002), mindset framing (Implicit Theories of Intelligence; Murphy & Dweck, 2016), Cognitive Appraisal Theory (Kemper & Lazarus, 1992), and privacy behavior (Wang et al., 2016) to the novel context: GenAI. This integration offers a deeper understanding of how mindset framing influences users' moral judgments regarding GenAI, with implications for both consumer psychology and information management.

While existing studies based on Implicit Theories of Intelligence (Murphy & Dweck, 2016) primarily focus on human actors, presenting the growth and fixed mindset concepts as related to human intelligence, this research extends this theory by applying these concepts to AI, specifically GenAI.

Furthermore, this research extends our understanding of Cognitive Appraisal Theory (Kemper & Lazarus, 1992) demonstrating how moral appraisals adapt in response to non-human agents providing insight on how mindset framing leads to different emotions regarding GenAI (So et al., 2015). Previous studies on emotions have chosen to approach valence as a predominant factor. However, this study extends earlier research (Kranzbühler et al., 2020), by

demonstrating that moral appraisals can create distinct emotional pathways that influence behavior in more complex ways than previously recognized. This reconceptualization underscores the need to consider psychological framing mechanisms in public discourse, policymaking and communication around AI technologies.

Furthermore, a key contribution of this work is the exploration of perceived morality as an underlying mechanism that determines emotional appraisals of GenAI and other advanced AI technologies. While prior research has examined the link between emotions, underlying appraisals, and action (Passyn & Sujun, 2006), studies have rarely focused on how these processes intersect with moral judgments about GenAI (for a notable exception, see Sullivan & Fosso Wamba, 2022). The findings regarding the mediation effect of perceived morality further extend the Implicit Theories of Intelligence (Murphy & Dweck, 2016) and the Cognitive Appraisal Theory (Kemper & Lazarus, 1992) by showing that GenAI mindset framing shapes moral judgments and results in downstream effects on emotional appraisals.

Our findings also reveal that GenAI mindset framing impacts privacy behavior, but only when GenAI expertise is considered. In doing so, this work builds on previous research into Privacy Calculus Theory (Wang et al., 2016). Specifically, we show that users' privacy behavior depends on their knowledge about these technologies and the mindset in which they framed them. Since a specific mindset framing is likely to result in different privacy behaviors (Dang & Liu, 2022a), this research identifies GenAI expertise as a boundary condition in the relationship between mindset framing and privacy behavior when assessing moral appraisals of AI-based technologies.

By integrating these theories, this work challenges conventional understandings of moral appraisals by offering a more dynamic, context-sensitive lens on GenAI's perceived morality. This theoretical contribution provides a foundation for future research on GenAI and morality, revealing moral appraisals as a fundamental, yet underexplored factor, of emotional responses to GenAI as a critical determinant of users' behavior.

4.2 Practical Implications

The findings help organizations across multiple sectors to understand the determining factors that influence users' moral perceptions, shaping the emotional responses towards GenAI and other AI-based technologies. Developments in this field are raising ethical questions (Goglin, 2023) and if users' moral judgments are more positive it may lead to more positive emotional responses.

Our findings provide insights to stakeholders that could lead to the improvement of customers' emotional responses towards their products and services based on GenAI, particularly, if they foster a growth mindset, to improve moral judgments about GenAI (Janssen & van Atteveldt, 2022). Considering that users have positive emotional appraisals when they have higher moral judgments towards GenAI, sectors such as marketing or tourism could create campaigns that highlight the ethical side of their AI-based products and services. Specifically, marketers could frame AI technologies as evolving and improving rather than static (growth mindset), developing campaigns that highlight AI's continuous learning capabilities. Organizations should explicitly communicate how GenAI technologies align with ethical principles, such as fairness, accountability, and privacy protection, to enhance user trust and to evoke positive emotional appraisals.

Marketing and information management practitioners can also benefit by gaining insight about how GenAI expertise moderates the privacy responses to GenAI and other AI-based technologies. This can inform strategies for targeted communication. For example, marketing messages tailored for low-expertise users could emphasize GenAI's adaptability and improvements, while messages for high-expertise users could address transparency and detail GenAI's ethical protocols. Based on our findings, companies should increase their knowledge about GenAI to improve trust regarding information disclosure while using these technologies. Offering training courses on technological literacy, communication actions or offering services with explanatory tutorials would be viable options. Noteworthy is the case of Portugal, where initiatives in this direction are already beginning to emerge in Directorate-General of Health (DGS), improving the perception of using GenAI chatbots in healthcare. By incorporating ethical AI in marketing, companies can differentiate themselves by positioning their AI-powered products and services as ethically responsible, aligning with user concerns regarding AI's moral impact.

Moreover, this research contributes to how managers integrate GenAI and AI agents into their companies by highlighting that employee acceptance toward these technologies varies based on the mindset framing and moral perceptions of the company's AI practices. If employees frame AI-based technologies in a growth mindset (rather than fixed), they may be more likely to accept integrating these tools in their work (Carr et al., 2012). For instance, organizations could implement training and internal communications, educating employees about GenAI's benefits, while emphasizing a growth mindset approach to AI integration. This includes launching employee GenAI acceptance programs and providing hands-on training and real-

world GenAI use cases to reduce resistance and improve employee engagement with these technologies. Managers should actively endorse GenAI as a tool for innovation and efficiency while addressing concerns about ethical risks.

Additionally, the findings of mindset framing may also be applicable to data collection strategies and user engagement. For example, businesses could optimize data collection and engagement by communicating on how AI personalization improves over time while maintaining ethical standards. This entails encouraging users to use AI-driven services by demonstrating tangible benefits, such as improved recommendations or enhanced user experiences. It would be also beneficial to integrate feedback mechanisms, allowing users to provide input on GenAI-driven services, reinforcing transparency and ethical responsibility in AI evolution.

4.3 Limitations and Future Research

This research acknowledges four key limitations that offer promising directions for future investigation. First, Study 3 revealed an unexpected moderating effect of GenAI expertise on privacy behavior. Participants with low expertise were more willing to disclose personal information under a growth mindset framing, while those with high expertise disclosed more under a fixed mindset. This pattern may reflect differing levels of risk awareness or sensitivity to data misuse. Future research could experimentally vary the degree of AI-related training to evaluate how expertise shapes responses to mindset framing. In addition, qualitative approaches, such as interviews with experts and non-experts, may also help clarify how GenAI knowledge influences disclosure decisions and contributes to the “privacy paradox” in AI-mediated contexts. Moreover, the regulated expression of disclosure vulnerability could be explored to deepen understanding of this paradox (Valenzuela et al., 2024).

Second, future research could explore how anthropomorphic features of GenAI systems influence user responses. Previous studies suggest that human-like cues (e.g., voice, interactivity, or facial expressions) can heighten emotional engagement and alter moral perceptions. Further studies could examine whether the presence or absence of anthropomorphic traits interacts with mindset framing in shaping emotional responses, privacy behavior, and moral judgment. Experiments could manipulate GenAI human-likeness and use neuromarketing tools, such as skin conductance or facial recognition, to capture emotional responses more precisely (Blut et al., 2021).

Third, additional research is needed to investigate the potential mediating role of empathy in the relationship between mindset framing and user responses to GenAI. Empathy is known to influence moral evaluations and could be a key mechanism in how users respond to emotionally expressive AI. Future studies could contrast feeling (vs. thinking) oriented AI systems and assess whether empathy mediates the observed effects (Huang, Rust, and Maksimovic 2019; Rust and Huang 2021). Longitudinal designs may further uncover whether sustained interactions with empathic AI shift privacy decisions and trust over time (Bigman & Gray, 2018).

Lastly, further work should explore how identity-related factors and agency transference interact with mindset framing and GenAI expertise. As users increasingly engage with AI in decision-making roles, it becomes important to understand when they align with or resist AI recommendations, particularly in relation to perceived autonomy. Future research could examine whether these dynamics are moderated by mindset framing or privacy concerns, and whether users actively retain control or defer to AI systems. These insights would help clarify how agency transference influences the perceived morality and acceptability of AI-assisted decisions, especially given the potential of agency transference to AI threaten human autonomy (Valenzuela et al., 2024).

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Appendix. Experimental Procedures and Measures

Study 2

AI Growth Mindset condition

“Artificial intelligence can mature and change their intelligent capabilities over time. These are malleable and can be cultivated. Some intelligent technologies continuously develop their learning capabilities, adapt their learning processes, and engage in continuous self-improvement. This reveals a growth mindset. Artificial Intelligence analyzes and enhances their own performance, updating their algorithms and competence level. When faced with challenges or ambiguous situations, these intelligent technologies approach problem-solving with an adaptive and growth mindset.

Take a moment to reflect on a situation related to artificial intelligence in which a technology's capabilities were developed through effort, learning, and perseverance (growth mindset). Please describe it in a few words in the box below.”

AI Fixed Mindset condition

“Artificial intelligence can't mature and change their intelligent capabilities over time. These are fixed and can't be cultivated. Some intelligent technologies don't continuously develop their learning capabilities, can't adapt their learning processes, and don't engage in continuous improvement. This reveals a fixed mindset. Artificial Intelligence is unable to analyze and enhance their own performance, keeping immutable their algorithms and competence level. When faced with challenges or ambiguous situations, these intelligent technologies approach problem-solving with an immutable and fixed mindset.

Take a moment to reflect on a situation related to artificial intelligence in which a technology's capabilities were fixed traits that could not be changed. (fixed mindset). Please describe it in a few words in the box below.”

Human Growth Mindset condition

“Human intelligence can mature and change their intelligent capabilities over time. These are malleable and can be cultivated. Some humans continuously develop their learning capabilities, adapt their learning processes, and engage in continuous self-improvement. This reveals a growth mindset. Humans analyze and enhance their own performance, improving their capabilities and competence level. When faced with challenges or ambiguous situations, they approach problem-solving with an adaptive and growth mindset. They learn from trial and error and find creative solutions to improve their abilities.

Take a moment to reflect on a situation related to human intelligence in which a person's capabilities were developed through effort, learning, and perseverance (growth mindset). Please describe it in a few words in the box below.”

Human Fixed Mindset condition

“Human intelligence can't mature and change their intelligent capabilities over time. These are fixed and can't be cultivated. Some humans do not continuously develop their learning capabilities, can't adapt their learning processes, and don't engage in continuous self-improvement. This reveals a fixed mindset. Humans are unable to analyze and enhance their own performance, keeping immutable their capabilities and competence level. When faced with challenges or ambiguous situations, they approach problem-solving with an immutable and fixed mindset. They don't learn from trial and error and can't find creative solutions to improve their abilities.

Take a moment to reflect on a situation related to human intelligence in which a person's capabilities were fixed traits that could not be changed (fixed mindset). Please describe it in a few words in the box below.”

Study 3

GenAI Growth Mindset condition

FindHotel: Your New Travel Partner

FindHotel is a new mobile app for travel powered by Generative AI: It employs high-performance machine learning that deeply analyses extensive consumer information to provide personalized travel recommendations.

FindHotel uses growth-oriented advanced algorithms capable of predicting your travel behavior and preferences: FindHotel uses growth algorithms that continuously develop its predictive abilities with more comprehensive and detailed personal data processing to enhance your travel planning experience.

Take a moment to reflect on FindHotel Travel App with deep personal data processing. Please write down your thoughts and impressions about FindHotel App in the box below.

GenAI Fixed Mindset condition

FindHotel: Your New Travel Partner

FindHotel is a new mobile app for travel powered by Generative AI: It employs low-performance machine learning that softly analyzes limited consumer information to provide personalized travel recommendations.

FindHotel uses fixed-oriented basic algorithms capable of predicting your travel behavior and preferences: FindHotel uses fixed algorithms that develop its predictive abilities with minimal and less intrusive personal data processing to enhance your travel planning experience.

Take a moment to reflect on FindHotel Travel App with minimal personal data processing. Please write down your thoughts and impressions about FindHotel App in the box below.

Measurement Items

Construct	Items	References
Moral Dimensions (Study 2)	Moral	Graham et al. (2011, 2013)
	Safe	
	Empathetic	
	Fair	
	Loyal	
	Solidary	
	Legal	
	Respectful	
	Innocent	
Emotional Appraisals - Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (Studies 1 and 2)	Interested	(Watson et al., 1988)
	Distressed	
	Excited	
	Upset	
	Strong	
	Guilty	
	Scared	
	Hostile	
	Enthusiastic	
	Proud	
	Irritable	
	Alert	
	Ashamed	
	Inspired	
	Nervous	
Determined		
Attentive		
Jittery		
Active		
	Afraid	
Privacy Behavior (Study 3)	I am willing to reveal my data with FindHotel app.	Zhang et al. (2023)
	I will probably reveal my personal information with this app.	
	I will reveal my personal information with FindHotel app.	
Generative AI Expertise/ knowledge (Study 3)	Never heard of Generative AI.	Huisman et al., (2021)
	Heard of Generative AI.	
	Basic knowledge of Generative AI.	Vorobeva et al., (2022)
	Intermediate knowledge of Generative AI.	
	Advanced knowledge of Generative AI.	
	Active Generative AI research/development.	